

SPORTS AND OTHER FORMS OF PHYSICAL ACTIVITY IN THE REHABILITATION OF THE DISABLED

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Abstract

The axiological values of sport are a cultural element uniting individuals in the rehabilitation of people with disabilities. Sport also plays an important role in the comprehensive restoration of lost functions, and its dissemination through media has led to it reaching a larger number of disabled people, influencing their choices and perceptions of reality. This is particularly important in view of the decreasing number of handicapped persons interested in practicing various sports or other forms of physical activity. Representation and the publicising of biographies and the achievements of athletes with disabilities and other people in what is broadly understood as physical culture is a proper method of promoting movement, which in the case of the disabled, becomes an additional means of their revalidation. Unfortunately, media coverage of many sporting events and other physical activities of people with disabilities has been underrepresented. There is also a lack of competition transmissions, including the Paralympic Games. This is because the media, in the pursuit of profit, do not shape proper attitudes towards disability in the public eye and poorly promote the profiles and achievements of disabled athletes.

Key words: sport, disability, media

Sport unites people and is the most widespread form of culture [11]. In our times, it has undergone various transformations (through globalisation, commercialisation, professionalisation, etc.) and created a series of connections with: economy, politics, economics, business and the media. That is why modern sports have less and less in common with those of antiquity [17, 3], while the aforementioned changes and dependence on numerous factors are the cause of a deep crisis visible in its brutalisation, violence, commercialism, corruption or doping. For this reason, among others, faith in the driving force of sports ideals has been undermined [7].

Sport and other - sometimes ordinary, everyday - physical activity is one of many forms of revalidation. It helps the disabled to restore lost functions to the maximum possible extent,

and appropriate training supports a comprehensive rehabilitation process. Sport also restores confidence in one's own strength, regardless of achieved results, and the disabled, providing mutual support, are also an example for others who more strongly motivate each other to perform greater and more systematic efforts. Awareness of belonging to such a community gives pride, reinforcing self-esteem. The motives for practicing various disciplines by the disabled are different, but the most common include: a desire for self-fulfilment, improvement of physical fitness, further rehabilitation and increasing contact with society [2, 4]. Despite this, there is a reduction in the number of people with disabilities practicing sports in Poland [16].

Sport is also represented by the media that have become an inseparable part of life.

Nowadays, it is hard to imagine this activity without media or the media without sport. On one side these are fans, and on the other, athletes and often "stars" of great popularity [6, 10]. It turns out that the importance of sport grows not for economic reasons, but due to the development of media techniques [12]. The mediality of this phenomenon means indirectly creating what should be valuable. Therefore, fitness or beauty may become desirable, because they are often presented and to a great extent. The image influences a viewer's consciousness, shapes his/her worldview, system of values, choices made, activity, lifestyle, beliefs and mental state [13]. For this reason, disability in sport, via the mean, can have an actual impact on hindering the decline in interest regarding the performance of this activity by the disabled.

Unfortunately, the laws of the market place make the issue of disability unprofitable. Meanwhile, the public wants to watch the sporting challenges of this group of people, including the Paralympic Games. The Paralympics in London 2012 brought 4,237 players together from 164 countries, and the transmission was broadcast by 100 countries around the world (without Poland). The Olympic Games in London included 221 Polish representatives, while only 100 took part in the Paralympic Games. The first won 10 medals and came in 30th on the medal list, and the second – 36, and 9th position in the ranking. Media interest in the Olympics was enormous, while engagement in the Paralympics was small. At the Paralympics in Rio de Janeiro 2016, Poland was represented by 90 athletes, winning 39 medals: 9 gold, 18 silver and 12 bronze. In the medal classifications at the Brazilian championships, Poland achieved 10th place. This was a completely different situation than in the London games four years earlier. TVP made an effort to report the event live, and the audience was not small, which indicates that the Poles want to watch the Paralympics at the highest level. The phenomenon of the axiologisation of sport is associated with high media interest in the Olympics, despite the lack of clear successes of Polish representatives and

a low interest in the Paralympics, even though the success of the Paralympic athletes was enormous.

Personal examples, the involvement and achievements of people with disabilities in physical culture, ranging from sports and recreation to tourism, influence the increase in popularity of physical activity. The condition is to grant these events appropriate publicity. Media personalities such as: Jan Mela, Oscar Pistorius, Natalia Partyka, Philippe Croizon and Rafał Wilk are the best examples, even though many more examples of influential media activity in this field can be found.

JAN MELA. An accident resulted in the amputation of Mela's left lower leg and right forearm. His achievement in the area of extreme tourism was highly publicised. He succeeded in reaching both of the Earth's poles in one year together with traveller Marek Kamiński. Jan Mela was the first ever, youngest person to achieve this, and the first disabled person to achieve such an effort using a leg prosthesis.

The march to the North Pole lasted 10 days, and to the south - 15, in freezing and extreme weather conditions. Every moment was accompanied by fear, which at the same time, helped to avoid dangers, unusual emotions and the monotony of the area. The expedition was fascinating and boring at the same time, because everything around them was invariably snow-ice and white and blue. The North Pole was conquered by a miracle and superhuman effort. The expedition and the southern conquest were not planned. The scale of the media resonance gave birth to the natural need for another example of heroism. People were impressed that the North Pole had been conquered by an ordinary man, with illnesses, problems, and a disabled person, with whom more people identified than one could suppose. Numerous motivational meetings at various places (schools, hospitals, prisons, hospices, etc.) revealed the need to organise another trip, this time to the South Pole.

The physical activity and the boy's profile were made public by the media to a wider audience. Jan Mela was and is aware that the mediality of this extraordinary undertaking had

an impact on his life and the popularity he gained, and paradoxically thanks to a dramatic accident, could help others, including those with disabilities. That is why he has been invited to various types of motivational events, to schools, universities, hospitals, hospices, orphanages or penitentiary facilities, to motivate people to take action, to persuade them to change. His story shows that life can be subject to human fate, and yet, man is invincible because his true strength is faith and hope.

The activity described, supported by the disseminatory role of the media, fulfilled its task. The world has been shown the testimony of an unusual struggle by a young person to return to a normal life, which is unfamiliar to many adults. But this is not the end. The story about these amazing events has been transferred to the big screen in the form of the psychological drama titled "My Pole" [Polish: Mój Biegun]. Thanks to this, the success and conquering of the Earth's poles was again revived and thanks to the media, it was shown that, despite disability, it is possible to do great things. It opened the path to anything not limited by the mind. J. Mela claims that "if we try hard, we will succeed". It is important in describing this biography that the expedition to the pole was neither his idea nor his dream. The proverbial hand and purpose was given to him by someone else; he only undertook and faced the challenge. This shows that in the life of a disabled person, a support group (person) is necessary.

Active, extreme forms of tourism in the life of Jan Mela continue as he climbs mountains (Kilimanjaro, Elbrus, El Capitan). 9 people took part in the expedition to Kilimajaro, including 3 in wheelchairs and 1 blind person. Many people with disabilities, thanks to their physical activity and determination, are much more fit than many healthy people. Jan Mela met such people at the "Festival of Enchanted Songs" [Polish: Festiwal Zaczarowanej Piosenki] organised by Anna Dymna, to which he has been systematically invited. Contact with this environment resulted in the proposal to take part in conquering Kilimanjaro. Most of the participants of this trip are people greatly toughened, who care for their physical fitness every day. Apart from them, a

blind boy, a girl in a wheelchair and a man with cancer took part in the expedition. Reaching the summit was a secondary matter for Janek, the most important was the mutual support and complementing of one another's deficiencies, for example, taking the hand of the blind, doing anything needed for them or instructing them to use their incredible spatial imagination. On the expedition to Elbrus, 1 blind person and a participant without one lung (cancer) took part. And the El Capitan mountain is the best known climbing rock in the world. Mela became the co-author of "Between the Poles" [Polish: Między biegunami], and of the travel programme broadcast on Radio Krakow. The media also accompanied the several-month expedition to Asia organised by the foundation (Thailand, Cambodia, Vietnam, Laos, Myanmar, India, China, Mongolia, Russia). Interestingly, after reaching a given country, an additional challenge was moving around its territory, mainly hitchhiking.

The "Beyond Horizons" [Polish: Poza Horyzonty] foundation, created by Janek, is the answer to the huge need for support, help, motivation and the purchase of equipment and prostheses as well as the organisation of integrational projects (Elbrus, ING Marathon, El Capitan, Beskid Niski, Bieszczady). People invited to take part in the projects are happy to be able to train. People who do not often want to be rehabilitated suddenly start fighting! The Foundation's task is to infect others with energy and make people with disabilities feel valuable.

In an interview, Mela stated: "I have my mission here in this world. It's about giving positive kicks, about transferring energy from hand to hand, about sharing what we've got. It is also about making healthy people familiar with the disabled. Because it is easier to live on wheelchairs, be deaf, blind, without hands, if treated normally". And in another interview he says: "If not for the accident and everything good that came after it, today I would be drinking technical spirits on a bench with my friends. Traumatic experiences have put me on a different track of life". The experience he has gained from the trip to the Earth's poles is best reflected in his words: "impossible - is very often

our excuse. I believe that almost anything can be done with hard work". Mela thinks that disability is only a "physical condition", and real disability is a "state of mind", meaning something much worse. Fighting with the latter is a real struggle, it is learning a different way of thinking, an active life with one hand and moving about with a prosthesis. In one of his interviews he said, "for sure, many of my traits have been strengthened by this accident. It has shown me that every problem, every difficulty, can be solved. I am living proof that anything is possible".

OSCAR PISTORIUS. As a result of the inborn absence of fibula bones, this track-and-field athlete underwent the amputation of both legs. He was an athlete competing with the best, and also with able-bodied players. Sport restored his self-confidence, functional and sport-related fitness, despite having prostheses. He was noticed, his athletic career blossomed quickly and he started to achieve results just as quickly. His debut took place at the Paralympic Games in Athens (2004), but then, his imagination went further, he dreamed of competing at the Beijing Olympics (2008), with able-bodied athletes. The media, press and the opinions of specialists in the field of biomechanics gave him an advantage over healthy competitors. Nevertheless, he was not allowed to compete with them. Pistorius appealed, and the appeal was recognised. He took part the Beijing Games. There, he won three gold medals - (100, 200, 400 meters), and achieved Olympic qualifications only 4 years later during the London Olympics in London (2012).

Persistence, determination, faith, fame and the magic of sport contributed to effects in revalidation. Pistorius became the first disabled athlete in history to come in 8th at the Olympic Games in London. Media admiration throughout the world praised his determination and courage. He was ever present among television and press headlines. Once again, the strength of sports in the media has proved that breaking barriers is possible. The pride of this South African citizen was even greater because his successes, were paradoxically beyond racial divisions and disability, and he grew as a symbol of the continuous struggle of the difficult history of his

hometown. The social recognition which he experienced was strengthened by his personal conviction that sport is a powerful ally in overcoming racial barriers.

Despite numerous hardships and rejection, but thanks to the consequences and support of various environments through sport and its media values, society has been shown that anyone can achieve their goals and dreams. Unfortunately, in subsequent events Pistorius committed murder, but this is a separate problem. In his book entitled "The secret of Oscar Pistorius" J. Carlin, Pistorius' biographer wrote: "After the death of his mother, there was no one in his life who had the wisdom and authority to bring him down to earth, to see that the young man had fallen victim to his own success and needed help in reconciliation with his disability, with the restrictions his mother taught him to deny, he stopped growing-up at the level of turbulent adolescence, he was too immature to cope with fame and money (...). He was a teenager in an adult body and, like a teenager, he became involved in unwise fascinations with women in which he saw the reflection of his mother, with the dangerous charm of weapons and fast cars".

Oscar's biography is a ready-made screenplay: disability from birth - prostheses and sports at the highest level – a life full of successes - admiration - popularity - and decline. This last epilogue of his life, and his cruel act of murder, have again led to the activity of the press, television and the Internet: notoriety in the shadow of drama, tragedy and the fall of a man with a beautiful sports history in the background. Later: investigations, courtrooms, conviction and guilt for the crime. The media - through which the world and millions of disabled people, for whom he was certainly a role model, saw him - this time, condemned him, and the film about this event and earlier events entitled "Oscar Pistorius: Blade Runner Killer", was created in 2017 and advertised with the significant slogan: "Heart of a champion, mind of a murderer".

NATALIA PARTYKA. Is a table tennis player, a person of disability, and a representative of the national senior team with global successes in this given discipline. She

was born without a fully developed forearm but she competes with healthy competitors, although a lack of forearm has caused, for example, loss of balance and other minor physical problems, which give non-disabled people an advantage over her. She says that she is looking for methods to cope with these and other losses in health. This approach to barriers builds faith in one's abilities, being a positive example for others.

She started training at the age of 7 and did not have to wait long for success. After qualifying for the low-level disability category (Class C-10), she appeared in Sydney (2000) at the age of 11. She was the youngest athlete in history at the Paralympics. Later, there were only gold medals from the Paralympic Games: Athens (2004) - she would say, "the final was too easy, empty stands, nobody expected anything from me", Beijing (2008) - "I saw crowds of people" and London (2012) - "It was a horror, but I managed". She also participated three times at the Olympic Games in Beijing, London and Rio, competing with healthy players. In the last Games, she was the only competitor from representative of Poland and one of the few people of disability from around the world.

Constant and not accidental successes have resulted in great interest in her person. The national and foreign press wrote about her that: "This Polish teenager creates the history of table tennis" (Deccan Herald, India); "Natalia Partyka creates history despite the lack of Pistorius" (Belfast Telegraph, Ireland); "The Polish woman can even win a medal in team competitions" ("San Diego Union Tribune USA). Furthermore, extensive articles can be found about Natalia's story and achievements, her way to Beijing, Polish tennis and Olympic struggles ("Die Welt", Germany; "Deccan Herald", India; "San Francisco Chronicle", USA; "Belfast Telegraph"); Ireland; "Sueddeutsche Zeitung", Germany; "Sueddeutsche. WNBC", USA) and analysis of game technique ("The Gazette", Canada). The publicity in various media about her comprises 70% of all publications that have appeared on the Paralympics and the greatest recognition. Over 90% of information about N. Partyka appeared on online portals. They constituted the

majority of references (5% press, 2.1% television, 0.9% radio). Natalia's enormous popularity on the internet and social media has coincided with her awareness of the need to be present on the web. Internet users admire her for her courage, joy of life, passion and determination in achieving goals. For many people, including the disabled, she has become a role-model and a person motivating them to act. Natalia is one of the most recognizable athletes. Her medality, thanks to sports successes and overcoming her disability, was an opportunity for numerous awards, among others: she received the "Champion" title in "Sports Review" [Polish: Przegląd Sportowy] and the TVP plebiscite, being among a group of the 20 best athletes; achieving the distinction of "Woman of the Year 2012"; The Knight's Cross of the Order of Polonia Restituta; and the function of Polish Ambassador at the 2010 Expo in Shanghai and the title of vice-champion of the ETTU Champions League with the KTS Tarnobrzeg team, and also the KTS team championship of Poland.

To some extent, disability, persistence and determination, and later sports successes as well as popularity, also in the media, have shown that the revalidation process has brought about results. Natalia, despite her disability, is a physically and mentally fit person. However, this is not all. Paradoxically, when denied a scholarship by the city officials of Gdansk a few years later, she achieved success and recognition as a person of disability not only in table tennis, but by being generous with the "Natalia Partyka Scholarship Fund" [Polish: Fundusz Stypendyjny Natalii Partyki]. The motto of the foundation's activity are her words: "All I do not have is a hand, others have it worse". Her willingness to share with others was born out of personal tragedy and the fight against disability. And its revalidation in the social area has resulted in charity activity.

Her biography refers to a person who, despite disability, and thanks to determination as well as intense work, fights for the world's highest laurels. In this way, an attractive example and a positive image of a woman of disability and an athlete who is open towards others is created

at the junction of sports activities supported by the media. Means of mass communication, being a powerful tool, have decided the place of people of disability in society, especially in shaping attitudes and behaviour towards them among non-disabled people. In spite of this, people with disabilities are presented in the media usually in two extremely different ways, either as people who do not manage in life, and need help, or as heroes performing extraordinary deeds.

It is worth recalling that the "Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities", ratified by Poland in 2012, item 8(c), obliges countries to take action in raising public awareness of matters related to people of disability, strengthening respect for their dignity and rights, combating stereotypes and prejudices and promoting knowledge about the abilities of disabled people. Actions undertaken include, among others, encouraging all media to present their image in a manner consistent with the aforementioned Convention, i.e. supporting, protecting and fully ensuring equal human rights and fundamental freedoms.

PHILIPPE CROIZON. Croizon is a man who underwent the amputation of arms and legs, after his limbs were lost in accident. After rehabilitation and a difficult period of adaptation to the new situation, as a result of strong will, determination and fascination with the story of another person who swam across the English Channel, this all allowed him to "learn" to swim and start regular trainings, first at the pool, then in the sea. In this case, we can see the noble influence of the media, and their missionary role indirectly showed Philippe the right way out of disability (the words of Janek Mela). The activity of this man, covered by the images and message of the media, showed evidence of a serious disability, high efficiency and motivation beyond the ability of average healthy people. The Frenchman, alone but belayed, crossed the English Channel (34 km in 14 hours) and covered four straits connecting all five continents, from Papua New Guinea to Indonesia (20 km in 7h 30'), from Egypt to Jordan, from Spain to Morocco, and from the USA to Russia (4.3 km in 1h20'). While swimming, he covered the distances in a suit protecting himself against

the cold and used mono-flippers attached to the stumps of his legs and a tube through which he could breathe with his face under water. His swimming feat as shown in the media gave testimony to the abilities of a man with a serious health loss. Everyone could witness what he did, but success would not have been possible without prior training. Two years were dedicated to preparation. This attitude allows people with disabilities to pursue dreams, gain social recognition and be an example to others. In an interview given immediately after the passage of the English Channel, he said, "I wanted to overcome my disability and win". On other occasions, he said: "I climbed my swimming Mount Everest because I wanted to show the world a different side of life for people with disabilities"[1]. After travelling from the USA to Russia, he stated that it was the most difficult thing in his life, and he dedicated the feat to all handicapped people, saying: "let this be an inspiration for others with disabilities". His swimming achievements broadcast by the media are, as quoted by Philippe: "hope and encouragement for the disabled around the world". By his example, he wants to tell them that: "anything is possible, we can all succeed in life even if we are crippled, there is no difference, we are all equal".

His achievements also include participation at the Dakar Rally, a race extremely demanding even for healthy players. The route of the rally (9 stages, where he assumed 54th place out of 58 in the general classification) was covered as a driver in a specially adapted car. Before this race, he also took part in rallies but of lower rank, where he achieved results according to his abilities. The media followed him step-by-step, reporting the event. And in the story about reaching his next goal, another athlete also appeared - Qatari Nasser Al-Attiyah, who supported the Frenchman financially. Would the sponsor's loyalty have been possible without Philippe's popularity? The answer to this question still remains open, but the probability does not. The intensity with which Philippe survives his life is difficult to achieve by many healthy people. Paradoxically, he owes his success to great tragedy, but later, to a good and

courageous decision. This impulse gave him media popularity, which prompted sensitive and affluent people and those who were an example for him, enabling the abandonment of "mental disability". Philippe has achieved a lot and will continue to succeed, despite numerous barriers. Conquering disability has changed his life. Determination and commitment to fight made him turn the negative consequences of his accident - his personal tragedy - into success. This shows the character of a positive, exemplary hero, both for those healthy and disabled.

RAFAŁ WILK. Wilk is a former speedway racer who suffered a serious accident during a competition. Currently, a paraplegic with paresis of the lower limbs, he is confined to a wheelchair, and is a disabled athlete who practices handcycling. He has achieved great success in this discipline. He is a 2-time Paralympic champion (London 2012, Rio 2016), a 4-time winner of the World and European Cup, a 5-time world champion and has been in 1st place on the UCI ranking five times. Sport, after a period of trauma, brought him back to society and offered a new dimension to his life. Apart from cycling, he also performs mono-skiing and is an academic teacher lecturing in the subject: Sport of the Disabled.

His life motto is hard work. Thanks to that, he defeated the disability, succeeding as an athlete and teacher, proving to himself and others that life after speedway and the accident still exists, because you can always find a new, different way. By his example, he shows that even when something goes wrong, we can be reborn. In sporting society, he is called "Man of Steel", because despite tragedy, he never gave up.

The media gave considerable coverage to his accident. Nobody thought that he would be able to find his place in sport again. However, he did not give up, he found himself a new discipline and very quickly began to be successful. Huge persistence and determination, despite the adversities of fate allowed him to win medals and make his dreams come true. Overcoming disability also has its social dimension through the activity of the foundation "Sport is One"

[Polish: Sport Jest Jeden]. The goal of this organisation is to support athletes with disabilities, so that "they can fulfil their dreams of medals and sports success". Sport is Rafał's greatest passion, which he carries out with great commitment. The accident undermined the possibility of speedway racing, but as he says, "it opened a path to a new discipline, I take advantage of this opportunity every day, I give my all at both practice and competitions".

His life after the accident and full revalidation in the mental and social dimension can be and are a model for others. The achievements were noticed by the country's authorities, granting him two decorations: the Knight's Cross and the Officer's Cross of the Order of Polonia Restituta. Rafał Wilk's activity was also appreciated by "Sports Review" [Polish: Przegląd Sportowy], where in the organised plebiscite, he won the title of "Disabled Athlete of the Year". He is also the most recognisable Paralympian next to Natalia Partyka. Awards and distinctions are recognition for outstanding sports achievements in Paralympic disciplines and promoting Poland on the international arena. On this occasion, thanks to the media, the world once again saw "human fate" and an attitude worthy of imitating - he fell, suffered pain, but got back up. First, he helped himself and succeeded. Now he helps others by passing on knowledge and life experience to University students and those with disabilities through the work of foundations. About himself he says, "I could play the role of great tragedy or simply take life into my own hands, enjoy it and live to the fullest. I chose the second option". Accident, disability and the "strength of sport" paradoxically changed his approach to the challenges posed by everyday life. Our hero is fully aware of this, stating that: "If not for disability and the wheelchair, I would not be a 5-time world champion, I would not go to the Paralympic Games, I would not bring home medals. I would also not know a lot of people who I met thanks to the fact that I am in a wheelchair". Among his other statements, are many wise thoughts encouraging and inspiring others to live better and make choices in achieving goals, and not those big ones, but also those small, everyday,

ones: "everything starts in our head"; "I do not see impossible things, some just require a little more time"; "In the worst situations, one must recognize the good sides - we always have a choice".

Rafał Wilk found his place on cycling routes and became the undisputed leader in this discipline. His dreams have become real again, but competitions are not everything. During these races he repeatedly emphasises that he is competing for Podkarpacie, becoming the ambassador of this region in Poland and abroad. He promotes a healthy lifestyle and the pursuing of dreams, despite all, and thanks to successes and their publicity, his activity and "plan for life" reaches those who need it better. His example is extremely important, as research shows that athletes with disabilities are an example of how to overcome their own weaknesses and barriers, they are admired and can be an inspiration for young people; and society positions athletes of disability at the same level as non-disabled athletes. Interest in a discipline depends on success and medals which activate media activity. The combination of these dependencies is empirical and translates into the phenomenon of revalidation via sport. Unfortunately, this principle is neglected by the Polish media, whose intention can only be seen in theory. It turns out that many Paralympic medallists are completely unknown, and their successes at European or world championships are not even mentioned. Meanwhile, as shown in research, 20% of the population are interested in sports of athletes with disability and the same number of people follow their successes and career, while 14% simply like all sports, including those performed by the handicapped.

The selected examples show that disabled athletes, with the support of the media, have overcome numerous barriers, and their limitations were not a permanent social condition, but were a stage in their psychosocial development. Invalidity did not stop them from carrying out ambitious goals, but was an

additional means of motivation and a driving force in constant readiness for further development. The activity in physical culture of each of these people has been shown by the media as people who train, engage in demanding disciplines and face new challenges. The degree of difficulty was often so great that healthy people representing an average fitness level could not manage as much as their disabled peers. Physical effort requires extraordinary fortitude and great work from the disabled. The media shows people wanting to overcome their own weaknesses. In their statements, they show humility and modesty, saying, among other things: "it could always be worse", "I am almost like you" [14].

Conclusion

1. The public want to watch sports events with the participation of disabled people, and the media can significantly initiate changes in the way of thinking about people affected by disability.

2. Axiologisation of sport is a concept attributed to the media and is an unfavourable phenomenon. The mass media, in the pursuit of profit, do not shape proper attitudes towards the disabled, including athletes, and thus, they do not fulfil the missionary obligation written in law.

3. Sport should be considered one of the most important elements of the rehabilitation process among disabled people, especially in the aspect of social integration.

4. Promoting the profiles, images, achievements and biographies of disabled athletes by the media is a chance to change the social reception of people affected by disability. Showing the struggle of these people within the specificity of the practiced discipline and with their own weaknesses, is a testimony of independent and autonomous people who are not only able to compete with those who are non-disabled, but can also be a role-model.

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